

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Strategies for Enhancing Teaching of Mechanical Trade through the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Facilities in Technical Colleges for Self-Employment in Kogi State, Nigeria

Authors

Udemadu, Obiora Chimezie¹ & Boniface Ugochukwu Ezeora²

Authors	Affiliation
1 st 2 nd	Department of Technology and Vocational Education (TVE) Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu

Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to examine the strategies for enhancing teaching of mechanical trade through the use of information and communication technology (ICT) facilities in technical colleges for self-employment in Kogi state. Three research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Three technical colleges were used for the study. The population of the study comprised 227 teachers and students of mechanical trades, in three technical colleges. The population is manageable; therefore, there was no sampling of the study. The instrument used for data collection was 29 items structured questionnaire, based on five points rating scale. The instrument was validated by two specialists in Department of Technology, School of Science Education, Enugu State University of science and technology (ESUT) Enugu and one in measurement and evaluation department, of MCE, ESUT. The reliability co-efficient of 0.75 was obtained after subjecting the instrument to pre-test. The instrument was administered by the three research assistants and was collected after completion. Statistical package for social science (SPSS) was used to compute mean for each research question and z test for the two null hypotheses. The findings revealed that ICT facilities are unavailable for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State. Besides that, Teachers are not having sufficient skills in using ICT packages and finally, there are constraints affecting the application of ICT packages in technical college Yola. Therefore, the researcher recommended that, Kogi state government as a matter of urgency, should provide adequate ICT facilities and packages to the state technical colleges, and prepare a conducive atmosphere for the application of the above-mentioned facilities.

Keywords: Mechanical Trade; ICT Facilities; Kogi State; Enhancing Teaching

Introduction

A technical college is an institution that provides courses in technology, science, business and crafts. A Technical College is also an educational institution that prepares students for a career in a specific field. Students are taught skills that are relevant to their vocational area only. It prepares students for careers at various levels, ranging from trade to lifelong craft practice and for educational furtherance in engineering, technology and business (Oluwatumbi, 2019). Technical colleges in Nigeria are established purposely to produce craftsmen at the craft level and master craftsmen at the advanced craft level (Audu, Aede & Muhammad, 2014). The training programmes of technical colleges are classified into clusters of areas of specialisation, termed as trades. National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB, 2019) identified trades offered in Nigerian technical colleges, which include building, electrical, welding and fabrication, agricultural implement and equipment mechanics work, auto electrical work, auto mechanics work, auto body building, auto parts merchandising, air conditioning and refrigeration, mechanic work, foundry craft practice, instruments mechanics work and mechanical engineering craft practice, among others. Amadi, Choirlu and Obed (2016) described mechanical trade as a general name used to describe trades that have direct bearing with metal welding, farming and servicing, and repair of machines, equipment and appliances. Mechanical trades comprised welding and fabrication, agricultural implements and equipment mechanics work, air conditioning and refrigeration, auto parts electrical, auto body building, auto mechanics work, auto merchandising, foundry craft practice, instruments mechanics work and mechanical engineering craft practice (NABTEB, 2019).

There are teaching methods and instructional strategies that take cognisance of the learners' interests, needs, problems, hopes, and aspirations while providing adequate full engagement or active participation in learning activities. Wali (2017) defined teaching as an intentional activity in the form of inter-personal influence aimed at changing another person's behaviour in the desired direction. There have been vigorous searches for strategies to improve the quality of instruction in schools and subsequent students' learning outcomes. Extrinsic and intrinsic related strategies are always employed to gain huge success in teaching and learning in schools. The extrinsic-related strategies are those strategies teachers adopt to make teaching and learning interesting and appreciative, while intrinsic-related strategies are the attributes and attitudes of students to make teaching and learning effective. Strategies mean various measures that could be used by teachers, including mechanical trade teachers, to improve the use of ICT facilities and achieve success. This implies that mechanical trade teachers should plan, organise, and control the available human and material resources of the school in order to achieve success (Idenyi & Owo, 2018). One of the strategies used in teaching mechanical trade teachers is the use of ICT facilities.

Graduates of mechanical trades are expected to acquire practical skills as well as basic information and communication technology (ICT) literacy to enable them to maintain modern motor vehicles, machine tools, powered equipment, and automation systems and to diagnose a variety of vehicle computer and computerised Components, replace faulty components and parts as needed (Robert, 2017). The above roles of craftsmen and technicians can only be realistic if information and communication technology is integrated into technical colleges because the impact of ICT cannot be over-emphasised in the area of skills acquisition and self-reliance. ICT has ability to enhance skills acquisition, quality delivery, and critical thinking and offers unlimited means of achieving academic goals (Gabriel, Olaniyi & Saliu, 2018). According to Oluwatumbi (2019) teaching and learning of technical trades demand engagement of students with array of ICT facilities that will arouse the interest of students. Adegbemile (2016) identified ICT packages that can promote skill acquisition and self-reliance in mechanical trades include computer-assisted instruction, web-based system, computer-aided design, auto-card, graphic package, powerpoint application, tutorial, computer conferencing, internet, interactive video CD-ROM and others.

Summak and Mustafa (2017) further confirmed that ICT facilities can accelerate, enrich and deepen basic skills and motivation and engage students in academic experiences. Consequently, most graduates of mechanical trades are deficient and do not possess the requisite skills needed in the labour market due to the recent increase in the incorporation of modern technology in motor vehicle and machine tools industries (Babalola & Yaduma, 2016). Therefore, this study examined the strategies for enhancing the teaching of mechanical trade through the use of information and communication technology (ICT) facilities in technical colleges for self-employment in Kogi state

Statement of the Problem

The recent increase of modern technology incorporated into modern motor vehicles and mechanical tools has brought about enormous challenges in operation, repairs, and maintenance services. These challenges include a lack of qualified craftsmen and technicians with the requisite skills to test and diagnose certain troubleshooting and to carry out repairs and maintenance operations. Another challenge is poor service rendered by craftsmen and technicians, which has increased unemployment among mechanical trades graduates. These challenges are against the goals of technical and vocational education in Nigeria, as stated in the National Policy on Education because craftsmen and technicians are expected to have the requisite skills, attitude and knowledge to meet the demands of society. Therefore, this study examined the strategies for enhancing the teaching of mechanical trade through the use of information and communication technology (ICT) facilities in technical colleges for self-employment in Kogi state.

Purpose of the Study

The study's main purpose is to examine the strategies for enhancing the teaching of mechanical trade through the use of information and communication technology (ICT) facilities in technical colleges for self-employment in Kogi state.

This study specifically examined:

1. The availability of ICT facilities for teaching mechanical trades in Technical Colleges in Kogi State.
2. The teachers' skills in using ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in Technical Colleges in Kogi State.
3. The constraints to teachers' strategies on the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trade in Technical Colleges in Kogi State.

Research Questions

This study answered the following questions:

1. To what extent are ICT facilities available to teach mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State?
2. What are the teachers' skills in using ICT packages to teach mechanical trades in technical colleges at Kogi State?
3. What are the constraints to teachers' strategies on the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in Technical Colleges in Kogi State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean response scores of teachers and students on ICT skills possessed for applications of ICT packages for teaching Mechanical trades in Technical Colleges in Kogi State.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between professional and non-professional teachers in terms of the constraints affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State.

Significant of the Study

The findings of the study will be of great benefits to students, teachers, parents, school administrators and employers of labour. Students will benefit from the findings of the study if ICT facilities are used to teach mechanical trade. This will arouse the interest of the students on the subject matter and skill acquisition that will help them to have gainful employment in the labour market.

Parents will benefit from the findings of the study if ICT facilities are introduced to teach mechanical trades. This will help the students acquire modern mechanical trade skills that will give them gainful employment, and in turn make the parents feel happy and expect support from their children in the near future.

Teachers will benefit from the findings of this study because it makes their lesson more interesting and practical orientation, this will help the teachers to achieve their objectives and good time management during lesson delivery.

School administration will benefit from the findings of this study by knowing the strengths and weaknesses and getting factual information on ICT integration in technical colleges. This will guide them on subsequent planning on ICT integration in schools.

Employers of labourers will benefit from the study's findings by the time the government improves from the weak areas identified and consider ICT integration in technical colleges a priority. This will lead to the production of graduates with skilful knowledge that will improve the labour market.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study used three Technical Colleges in Kogi State. The study population was comprised of 227 students and teachers of mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi state. There was no sampling for the study because the population was manageable; it was purposive. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire of 29 items based on a five-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by two specialists in the Technology Education Department, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu. The instrument was trial-tested using a sample of 20 respondents from Technical College, Nsukka, Enugu State, because of its contiguity with Kogi State.

The reliability coefficient of 0.65 was obtained using the Cronbach Alpha reliability test, meaning that the instrument was reliable for the study. The research assistants were properly trained in the administration of the instrument. The instrument was administered and retrieved after completion by the three research assistants. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used to compute the mean for each research question, and a z-test was used to test the two null hypotheses at a 0.5 level of significance. All items with a mean score of 3.50 and above were agreed, while items below 3.50 disagreed. Likewise, a Z-critical value less than the calculated value made the null hypothesis to be rejected; otherwise not rejected.

Result and Analysis

The results were presented in accordance with the research questions and the hypotheses.

Research Question 1: To what extent are ICT facilities available to teach mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State?

\bar{X}_a = mean Responses of students X_b = mean Responses of teachers

GM = grand mean Responses

Table 1: Mean response of teachers and students on the available ICT facilities for teaching mechanical trade in Technical Colleges in Kogi State

S/N	ITEMS	XA	XB	GM	REMARKS
1.	Voltage stabiliser	3.59	4.30	3.95	Available
2.	Internet connectivity	2.10	2.26	2.18	Not available
3.	Amplifier	2.04	2.12	2.25	Not available
4.	Source of electric power	2.18	2.04	2.51	Not available
5.	Grand Mean	2.00	2.49	2.25	Not available
6.	Computer systems	2.42	2.18	2.30	Not available
7.	Printer	2.03	3.10	2.57	Not available
8.	Scanner	2.43	2.33	2.88	Not available
9.	Photographic camera with accessories	3.72	3.46	3.59	Available
10.	Public address system with accessories	3.24	2.09	2.67	Not available
11.	Video camera with accessories	2.10	2.57	2.34	Not available
12.	Closed-circuit television	3.68	2.50	3.09	Not available
13.	Protector with accessories	2.20	2.54	2.37	Not available
	Grand Mean	2.59	2.61	2.69	Not available

Table 1, revealed that 2 out of 12 items on available ICT facilities for teaching mechanical trades in Technical Colleges in Kogi State are available; this is because the table shows that the 2 items were above 3.50, which is the cutoff point. This implies that ICT facilities are not available to teach mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State. This is evident because the value of the grand mean is 2.69, which not available the availability of ICT facilities in technical colleges in Kogi State.

Research Question 2: What were the teachers' skill in using ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical Colleges in Kogi State?

Table 2: Mean response of teachers and students on teacher's skills in using ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State

S/N	ITEMS	XA	XB	GM	REMARKS
13.	Presentation with the aid of PowerPoint packages	3.55	3.447	3.51	Agree
14.	Use auto-CAD package for designing	2.04	2.07	2.06	Disagree
15.	Use of ICT tutorial package	2.04	2.23	2.14	Disagree
16.	Use of webs-base system	2.11	2.44	2.18	Disagree
17.	Use of word process package	3.56	3.62	3.59	Agree
18.	Use of spreadsheet package	3.12	2.90	2.61	Disagree
19.	Use of computer-assisted instrument package	2.05	2.11	2.08	Disagree
20.	Access and retrieval of information on a particular database system	2.17	2.32	2.25	Disagree
21.	Browse and download documents from the internet	3.52	3.68	3.60	Agree
	Grand mean	2.68	2.85	2.76	Disagree

Table 2, shows that only 3 out of 9 items on the teachers' skills in using ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades were possessed. The grand mean was 2.79, which was below the cutoff point of 3.50. This suggests that teachers need to acquire more skills to enable them to use ICT packages in teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State.

Research Question 3: What were the constraints affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State?

Table 3: Mean response of teachers and students on the constraint affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State

S/N	ITEMS	XA	XB	GM	REMARKS
22.	Lack of personnel ICT train personal	3.18	3.93	3.56	Agreed
23.	Lack Maintenance culture	3.25	3.52	3.39	Disagreed
24.	Teachers resistance to change	3.52	4.10	3.81	Agreed
25.	Restriction from free access to ICT facilities	3.62	4.13	3.88	Agreed
26.	ICT facilities are only used during a practical lesson	4.02	4.23	4.13	Agreed
27.	ICT packages are not available	3.08	3.97	3.53	Agreed
28.	Teachers are not interested in using ICT facilities in classes	4.11	2.07	2.09	Disagreed
29.	Unstable electricity supply	4.10	4.38	4.24	Agreed
	Grand mean	3.61	3.79	3.70	Agreed

Table 3 revealed that 6 items were rated agreed while 2 items were rated disagreed, out of 8 items listed on the constraints affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi state. However, the grand mean 3.70 implies that there are constraints affecting the application of ICT packages in technical colleges in Kogi State.

Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁)

There is no significant difference between the teacher and students on the skills in using ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State.

Table 4: Z-test of the mean responses of teachers and students on the skills in using ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State

RESPONDENTS	X	SD	N	DF	Z-CAL	Z-CRIT	REMARKS
TEACHERS	2.85	0.95	16				
				2.5	0.07	1.72	Not Significant
STUDENTS	2.68	0.08	211				

Table 4 shows the z- calculated value 0.06 is less than z-critical of 1.72. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that the view of teachers and students on the skills in using ICT packages has no significant difference between the professional and non-professional teachers in technical colleges in Kogi state.

Null Hypothesis (H₀₂)

There is no significant difference between professional and non-professional teachers regarding the constraints affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State.

Table 5: Z-test of the mean responses of teachers and students on the constraints affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trade by professional and non-professional teachers in technical colleges in Kogi state

RESPONDENTS	\bar{X}	SD	N	DF	Z-CAL	Z-CRIT	REMARKS
TEACHERS	3.79	0.61	16				
				2.25	0.74	1.95	Not Significant
STUDENTS	3.61	0.23	211				

Table 5 shows that the z-calculated value of 0.74 is less than the z-critical value of 1.95. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that the constraints affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades by teachers and students in technical colleges are not significant.

Findings of the Study

The findings of the study were presented in accordance with the research questions and hypothesis that guides the study.

1. The grand mean of teachers and students on the available ICT facilities for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State is below the cutoff point. This means that ICT facilities are not available to teach mechanical trade in technical colleges.
2. The study revealed that teachers do not have sufficient skills in using ICT packages to teach mechanical trades in technical colleges. Move especially in auto-CAD, tutorial, web-based systems, and spreadsheets.
3. Constraints are affecting the application of ICT packages for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State. Such constraints include a lack of trained manpower personnel, poor maintenance culture, unstable electricity supply, unavailable ICT packages and others.

Discussion

The data presented in Table 1 answered research question 1. The findings show that the grand mean of teachers and students on the available ICT facilities needed for teaching mechanical trades rated 2.69. This means that there is a need for technical colleges in Kogi state to have more ICT facilities to enable teachers and students to improve in lesson delivery and skill acquisition. Robert (2017) also reported that most technical colleges in Nigeria have un-available ICT facilities for teaching technical trades. This was also confirmed by Shambirna'ah (2016), who opined that computers are the only ICT facility mostly found in Nigerian institutions.

The findings concerning research question 2, as shown in Table 2, revealed that teachers did not possess sufficient skills in using ICT packages to teach mechanical trades in Kogi State technical colleges. These findings agreed with Obakhume (2017), who revealed that there are inadequate ICT manpower personnel in technical colleges in Kogi state. This finding was also confirmed by Adeosun (2018), who reported that technical colleges have inadequate manpower to implement ICT in technical colleges in Lagos state.

The results shown in Table 3 revealed that constraints are affecting the application of the ICT package for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State. Adomi and Kpangban (2018) also identified factors that were found to be constraints affecting ICT application in schools. This includes lack of maintenance culture, lack of electrical power supply, lack of trained personnel and others. Dankaro and Jude (2016) agreed with the findings. Obakhume (2017) also revealed that infrastructure and internet connectivity are some constraints that affect ICT application in schools and colleges.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made. Teachers and students did not have available ICT facilities for teaching mechanical trades in technical colleges in Kogi State. Most mechanical trades graduates were left unemployed because they do not possess sellable skills for societal needs and development. Besides that, teachers do not have sufficient skills in using ICT packages to teach mechanical trades in technical colleges. This has affected technical college graduates, more especially mechanical trades graduates because they cannot solve complex problems related to new technology because they have not been trained with ICT facilities.

Finally, constraints are affecting the application of ICT facilities in teaching mechanical trades. These include a lack of trained manpower personnel, lack of ICT facilities, poor maintenance culture and unstable electricity supply.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommended the following:

1. There is an urgent need for government, non-governmental organisations and good-spirited individuals to provide technical colleges with modern ICT facilities.
2. A programme of in-service training for teachers of technical colleges in respect of ICT facilities should be put in place.
3. Power supply facilities should be improved upon to provide an enabling environment for the ICT facilities as they are provided.

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